

**DESIGN, ANALYSIS, TESTING, AND CERTIFICATION OF COMPOSITE PRIMARY
STRUCTURE FOR THE PIAGGIO P-180 AVANTI**

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ABSTRACT

With recent advances in composite analysis and testing, some of the advantages of composites over metals, such as lower weight and improved fatigue life, can be implemented on aircraft structures. One recent example is the Piaggio P-180 Avanti.

The Piaggio P-180 Avanti is a nine passenger twin pusher-turboprop engine business airplane, certified to Federal Aviation Regulation Part 23. It is a unique three lifting surface design aircraft (forward wing, main wing, horizontal stabilizer). The composite structural components include the forward wing, horizontal stabilizer, vertical fin, rudder, tail cone, engine nacelles, wing central trailing edge, radome, and baggage bay and landing gear doors. The composite components were designed, fabricated, tested and certified by the Composite Products Group of UTC/Sikorsky Aircraft (now Dow-United Technologies Composite Products, Inc.) under contract to the airplane manufacturer Rinaldo Piaggio SpA in Genoa, Italy. The composite designs include extensive use of co-cured structure to minimize weight and cost (e.g., the forward wing and horizontal stabilizer designs include a co-cure of the lower skin assemblies, spar webs and caps; the vertical fin and rudder assemblies consist of skins, spar webs, spar caps, and leading edge co-cured as one assembly).

The Special Conditions required for composite structures were addressed by full-scale structural testing in addition to extensive analytical substantiation. The procedure to design, analyze and test a complex composite aircraft structure under combined loading (static and fatigue) is presented. In particular, issues related to failure mode interaction such as buckling and material failure are considered. The importance and effect of environmental conditions is addressed. Good agreement between theory and experiment was observed.

The requirements for damage tolerance and their implications on static and fatigue testing of composite aircraft are discussed with specific mention to the number of test lifetimes required, limit and ultimate load tests and testing with and without damage.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Primary Aircraft Structure; Design/Analysis/Testing; Certification; Durability/Damage Tolerance

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in the design of aircraft structure has increased steadily over the last decade, and issues relating to composite certification have been addressed in other published literature (References 1-4). However, most of the applications have involved secondary structure (not affecting safety-of-flight). The smaller business/commuter FAR23 aircraft manufacturers are the first to design and produce airplanes with composite primary structure (Learfan 2000, Beech Starship, Piaggio P-180 Avanti). The use of composites in aircraft primary structure offer the advantages of lower weight and improved fatigue life. A discussion of the design, analysis, testing, and certification philosophy for composite structure for the Piaggio P-180 Avanti is presented in this paper.

In 1983, the Composite Products Group of UTC/Sikorsky Aircraft (now Dow-United Technologies Composite Products, Inc.) was awarded a contract by Rinaldo Piaggio SpA to design and manufacture composite components for the Piaggio P-180 Avanti. The contract included design responsibility for the forward wing, horizontal stabilizer, vertical fin, tailcone, rudder, engine nacelles, wing central trailing edge and other control surfaces, radome and baggage bay and landing gear doors which are illustrated in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Composite components on the Piaggio P-180 Avanti.

The work package included materials development and qualification, structural full-scale testing and certification to the required Federal Aviation Regulations (FARs) and other special conditions for composite primary aircraft structure. Since the primary designer of the aircraft was Rinaldo Piaggio SpA, certification involved many different agencies, including Registro Aeronautico Italiano (RAI), the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) International Office

in Brussels, Belgium, FAA Small Airplane Directorate in Kansas City, MO, FAA-New England Region, and National Resource Specialists (NRS) from FAA-Washington, D.C., Long Beach, CA and Seattle, WA offices.

2. DESIGN

The design of the primary structure included extensive utilization of co-cured structure to avoid secondary bonding and fastening operations. Co-cured structure also minimizes weight and costs. Both the forward wing and horizontal stabilizer designs utilized a co-cure of the lower skin with the spar webs and caps, as depicted in Figures 2 and 3.

FIGURE 2. Forward Wing Assembly - lower skin cocured with spars, top skin, leading edge and fittings are bolted and bonded onto lower box assembly.

FIGURE 3. Horizontal Stabilizer Assembly - lower skin cocured with spars and leading edge, top skin and fittings are bolted and bonded onto lower box assembly.

The vertical fin assembly and rudder assembly included a co-cure of the skins, spar webs, and spar caps, which is illustrated in Figures 4 and 5.

FIGURE 4. Vertical Fin Assembly - vertical fin spars and skins cocured; bulkheads, tailcone skins and close-out ribs bolted and bonded.

FIGURE 5. Rudder Assembly - spars and skins in both rudder and trim tab cocured; balance horn, fittings, and close-out ribs bolted and bonded.

A wire mesh screen was incorporated into the outer mold line (OML) of the structure to provide electrical continuity for lightning strike protection. Titanium fasteners and paste adhesive were utilized to provide secondary assembly, as necessary. These joints were designed for redundancy with the paste adhesive capable of limit load and fasteners were utilized to ultimate load capability.

2.1 Special Design Conditions To comply with the special conditions of the FARs, many conservative design features were incorporated in the structure. The material properties utilized were representative of the worst environmental condition; elevated temperature wet (ETW), with full saturation. Typical conditioning of the test specimens were at an accelerated environment of 82°C and 87% R.H. to a minimum 1.1% weight gain representative of the worldwide environment. Based on the results of tension and compression open hole and impact testing at room temperature dry (RTD) and ETW environments, a strain value of .0045 was selected as the cut-off strain limitation for the graphite/epoxy material at ultimate load to achieve a damage tolerant structure. Strength analyses were conducted using classical laminated plate theory and the Tsai-Hill failure criterion.

A computer program, the Composite Laminate Analysis Method (CLAM), calculates the ply-by-ply stresses and strains based on input of the normal, shear membrane loads and bending moments (from the finite element model). The computer program then compares the applied stresses to the allowable lamina strengths ("B"-basis allowables at the critical environment) using the Tsai-Hill polynomial interaction/failure criterion. The laminate is assumed to have failed when the margin of safety for any ply has a value of zero or less. This "first-ply failure" could be the result of fiber failure or matrix cracking.

The NASTRAN finite element model was utilized extensively to model manufacturing flaws/defects. The use of composite laminate (PCOMP) property cards in the Finite Element Model allowed for simulating mislocated or missing plies in the laminate. The finite element model was also utilized to simulate thru-puncture damage to the structure by the removal of specific elements, to simulate bondline delaminations and to simulate fitting failures to show redundancy.

Required documents for certification included: an extensive stress report with finite element model results, a certification program plan, material allowables report, damage tolerance analysis report, lightning strike analysis and testing reports, and full-scale test plans and final reports.

2.2 Full-Scale Testing In addition to the analytical substantiation, the full-scale test articles contained unrepaired manufacturing defects, simulated bondline delaminations (teflon film inserted into bondline), impact damage (due to tool drop, hail, runway debris, etc.), skin punctures and skin and spar cuts to conservatively show that the structure was capable of all types of damage without significant effect. The types of damage inflicted on the full-scale test articles included simulation of dropped tools and parts, and damage from ground equipment, runway debris, hail, and engine wash.

Unlike previous full-scale testing of composite structure, an emphasis was placed on the affects of material variability and environmental condition. The forward wing and

empennage (vertical fin, tailcone, horizontal stabilizer and rudder) were environmentally conditioned to saturation at 82°C and 87% R.H. Coupon testing had verified that the ETW condition was the most critical. The environmental conditioning permitted demonstration of ultimate static load (and repeated fatigue loading) at the most critical environment for the material system.

Other aircraft certification programs have involved full-scale testing at RTD environments which then required further correlation with predicted RTD strain levels and additional substantiation that the environmental material effects could be analytically predicted and correlated with other sub-scale, element, and coupon tests. Full-scale testing of a fully-conditioned structure addresses any concerns in this area. The greatest problems with conditioning of a full-scale structure are size (transport category aircraft wing) and time (thicker laminates may need to condition over a period of one year or longer to reach saturation in accelerated environments).

2.3 Test Sequence The full-scale articles testing sequence is summarized as follows:

- Application of Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID)
- RTD Static Ultimate Load - Required to allow prototype to initially fly
- Environmental Conditioning to Saturation
- One Lifetime of Repeated Loads (Fatigue)
- ETW Static Ultimate Load
- Application of Visible Impact Damage (VID)
- One Lifetime of Damage Tolerance (Fatigue)
- ETW Residual Strength - Limit Load Every 9000 Equivalent Flight Hours and After 30,000 Hour Life
- ETW Severe Damage Demonstration - Limit Load
- Repair All VID and Severe Damage
- Ultimate Load Demonstration of Repaired Structure
- ETW Failing Load Demonstration

During all phases of testing, selected "hot spots" were monitored by strain gauges and/or acoustic emission sensors. All acquired data was stored in computer memory and on floppy disks for later review. During the more critical static ultimate load tests, selected strain gauges were plotted by hand at each load interval to quickly assess the criticality of the structure being monitored. All critical static load tests were witnessed by FAA or FAA - designee personnel. The fatigue tests were monitored on a daily basis by an FAA Designated Engineering Representative (DER). Periodic structural inspections were conducted by Sikorsky Aircraft inspection personnel and FAA Manufacturing Inspection Division Office (MIDO) personnel. All testing work was documented by Test Plans and the testing was reported in test results documents. Any changes were documented by appropriate paperwork or document appendices and approved by certifying agencies before commencement of work.

3. LESSONS LEARNED

The full-scale testing was not without surprises. Fortunately, many of the surprises occurred very early in the program and were quickly rectified. In the early stages of the forward wing static testing, the wing failed at about 120% limit load. The problem was attributed to the skin honeycomb core located in the incorrect ribbon direction. This caused premature core shear failure. Another forward wing specimen (with the core in the correct ribbon direction) successfully demonstrated ultimate load.

The empennage full-scale test article also experienced some problems during static testing. The tailcone skin (which was designed for post-buckling above limit load to save weight) started buckling prior to limit load. Since buckling is a stability phenomenon based on thickness, a wet lay-up skin repair was made to the test article. This repair allowed testing to continue to above limit load where, at about 110%, the skin started buckling again. With the skin post-buckled, one of the bulkheads experienced a buckle around a penetration area precipitating in a premature failure of the bulkhead and the tailcone skin. After a design review with the customer, it was mutually agreed to change the design of the tailcone skin to preclude buckling up to ultimate load (and accept the associated weight penalty) and to add beading to the bulkhead laminate web to also increase stability margin. After these modifications were made, the "new design" empennage successfully completed ultimate load, which permitted for the flight test program to begin. The full-scale test specimens were then placed into environmental chambers and conditioned at 82°C and 87% R.H. until laminate saturation equilibrium, prior to continuing into the durability/damage tolerance testing phases.

Two certification issues surfaced during the environmental conditioning phase of the test. The first issue was a result of flight testing. It became apparent during flight testing that the aircraft was flying at higher speeds than originally anticipated in the analytical aerodynamic studies. Rather than limit the performance of the airplane to the original design loads, Piaggio decided to take advantage of the 40 knot speed increase and reinforce the aircraft structure to the new higher loads. The resulting load changes required reinforcement of an inboard section of the forward wing skins and spars and some fastener changes. Changes to the empennage structure were much more subtle.

The original analyses for the empennage included some conservative assumptions. Initially, the critical design condition was a combination of "engine-out" side load on the vertical fin with a "gust down" horizontal stabilizer superimposed. This "double jeopardy" condition was unrealistic, and it was agreed that the events were singular. The new increased singular load events were about the as critical as the "double-jeopardy" condition. Some further risk reduction testing was conducted to eliminate concern over a stability margin on the horizontal stabilizer rear spar, as the result of the center of pressure moving aft. The only design changes to the horizontal stabilizer were fastener changes in some attachment areas.

The second certification issue was the selection of the fatigue spectrum for the

empennage. The original spectrum selected was based on a Boeing methodology for transport category (FAR 25) aluminum aircraft. Several meetings were held with FAA and RAI specialists to address the spectrum issue. The basic problem with an aluminum-based spectrum is that higher loads (usually above 70% limit load) are clipped from the spectrum because higher loads cause fatigue cracks to plasticize at the crack tip, negating any further growth until the crack can re-initiate outside the plastic zone. This retardation effect is not true of composites which do not yield and instead, fast fracture once a critical crack length is reached. At issue was also truncation of lower loads in the spectrum. Metal spectrum loads are traditionally truncated at the material endurance limit at about 10^6 cycles. Some in-house test data and published literature helped establish a strain-based truncation level for the graphite-epoxy material.

As a result of coordinated participation meetings with certification authorities, it was mutually agreed to clip high level loads above limit load (after application of acceleration factor), use a strain based truncation level method, and derive all the aircraft loads from NASA data on actual FAR Part 23 category aircraft. The resulting composite based fatigue spectrum, however, created one additional problem - how to handle the metal attachment fittings in the forward wing and horizontal stabilizer. This issue was resolved by utilizing FAA document AFS-120-73-2. By design, the fittings were fail-safe, with features for loss of redundancy. A safe life "Miner's Rule" cumulative damage analysis was used to safely show a minimum scatter factor of 8. This conservative analysis coupled with the fail-safe fitting designs, was used as certification basis to address the issue of metal fittings in a composite fatigue spectrum.

Testing was allowed to proceed once the new spectrum had been derived and approved. The one lifetime of durability testing was relatively trouble-free. The ETW ultimate load testing was also successful. Impact damage and skin cuts, beyond the threshold of detectability, were imposed on the structure and damage tolerance testing commenced. Damage was strain gauged and monitored with inspections every 3000 equivalent flight hours. No damage growth was reported on the impacts and saw cuts during the 30,000 flight hour lifetime.

The only other surprises during testing were the occasional noises where adhesive bond lines cracked as the result of ultimate load testing and impact damage at the bonded joints. No attempt was made to repair any cracked bondlines (since there were fasteners in the attachment areas). The noisier bonds were actively monitored by acoustic emission sensors, and periodically inspected every 9,000 equivalent flight hours. The criticality of the bondlines was further demonstrated when the test articles were taken to failure well in excess of ultimate load at the conclusion of testing. All inflicted damage (beyond threshold of detectability) was repaired by techniques established in field repair manuals (no repairs to bondlines or damage below detectable threshold) and was successfully demonstrated when the failing load tests exceeded ultimate load: 178% limit load for forward wing and 190% limit load for the empennage.

The damage tolerance testing was utilized to establish inspection intervals for the composite structure. The FAA Special Conditions for composite structure require the establishment of an inspection interval such that the damage initially becomes detectable before it exceeds the extent of damage for which residual strength has been demonstrated. A conservative scatter factor of 3 was applied to the demonstrated damage tolerance life, without growth. Another factor of 3 was established to allow an inspector at least two inspection periods where the damage could be missed by visual inspection.

The test articles had successfully demonstrated 30,000 hours of no damage growth. The 30,000 hours were reduced to 10,000 hours by the life scatter factor and then further reduced to 3,000 hours to take into account the missed inspection intervals. However, the established interval is currently 500 hours for production airplanes delivered to customers.

Strain gauge results from testings were compared with finite element model predictions. In general, reasonable correlation was established for larger details such as skins and spars. However, the finite element model (FEM) mesh was very coarse, with plate elements typically 3 to 4 inches in length. This was further complicated by other issues, such as the inability to model details, such as skin sandwich panel core ramp-down, without generating a more detailed model that would be cost-prohibitive and more difficult to run.

4. CONCLUSION

The Piaggio P-180 Avanti was certified in May, 1990. This culminated a program which started in December, 1983. The certification process was lengthy, with delays due to design changes and difficulties with establishing the proper fatigue spectrum for composite aircraft structure. Emphasis was placed on full-scale testing of structure in its most critical elevated temperature wet saturated condition. New policies were established to address concerns over the certification of novel (composite structure) aircraft design. The certification effort was international involving the working cooperation of the RAI, FAA, and the design companies. A great deal of time was spent in open discussion with the certifying agencies and everyone pulled together as a team. Without the cooperation of all these disciplines, the certification process would have been further complicated, resulting in a longer and more difficult resolution.

Earlier certification of the composite Beech Starship™ helped establish policy guidelines to make Piaggio certification a little easier. New problems were encountered in Piaggio certification, however everyone worked together to address these issues. As a result of work on the P-180, it is envisioned that the certification efforts of future composite aircraft manufacturer may have been made simpler and more defined. These guidelines will enable aircraft manufacturers to build safe, reliable aircraft that will ensure public confidence.

5. ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Mr. Johnson has been working in the aircraft industry for eleven years: six years for the Boeing Company in Seattle, WA and five years for UTC/Sikorsky Aircraft . He is currently with Dow-UT Composite Products, Inc. (a joint venture between UTC and Dow Chemical) as a Senior Project Engineer in the Structures Group. He has been involved in the design of composite primary aircraft structure for over 8 years. His work has included design, analysis, and testing for military fixed-wing aircraft and helicopter programs and has included the structural analysis and certification responsibilities for the composite structure on the Piaggio P-180 Avanti program. He holds a B.S. degree in Mechanical Engineering Technology from Cogswell College.

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